

ID	Title	Year	DOI
1	Underwater acoustic communication channels: Propagation models and statistical characterization	2009	https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.2009.4752682
2	Quasi-all-optical network extension for submarine cabled observatories	2011	https://doi.org/10.1117/1.3560542
3	An overview of the Internet of Underwater Things	2012	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inca.2012.07.012
4	A Comprehensive Study on the Internet of Underwater Things: Applications, Challenges, and Channel Models	2017	https://doi.org/10.3390/s17071477
5	Underwater Internet of Things in Smart Ocean: System Architecture and Open Issues	2019	https://doi.org/10.1109/TII.2019.2946618
6	Internet of ships: A survey on architectures, emerging applications, and challenges	2020	https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2020.2993411
7	A survey on underwater wireless sensor networks: Requirements, taxonomy, recent advances, and open research challenges	2020	https://doi.org/10.3390/s20185393
8	Enabling Sustainable Underwater IoT Networks With Energy Harvesting: A Decentralized Reinforcement Learning Approach	2020	https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2020.2990733
9	Recent Advances and Future Directions on Underwater Wireless Communications	2020	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11831-019-09354-8
10	Collaborative automation and IoT technologies for coastal ocean observing systems	2021	https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.647368
11	Internet of Underwater Things and Big Marine Data Analytics—A Comprehensive Survey	2021	https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2021.3053118
12	A systematic review on recent trends, challenges, privacy and security issues of underwater internet of things	2021	https://doi.org/10.3390/s21248262
13	Marine Data Sharing: Challenges, Technology Drivers and Quality Attributes	2022	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21388-5_9
14	Engineering Challenges of Stationary Wireless Smart Ocean Observation Systems	2023	https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2023.3283252
15	Synthesized Data Quality Requirements and Roadmap for Improving Reusability of In-Situ Marine Data	2023	https://doi.org/10.1109/RE57278.2023.00016
16	Survey on communication and networks for autonomous marine systems	2019	https://doi.org/10.1007/s10846-018-0833-5
17	Quality control for ocean observations: From present to future	2022	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11430-021-9846-7
18	Ocean Data Product Integration Through Innovation-The Next Level of Data Interoperability	2019	https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00032
19	Security challenges of Internet of Underwater Things: A systematic literature review	2020	https://doi.org/10.1002/ett.4203

ID	Challenge	Layer	Quality Attribute Impacted	Quality of Data Product Impacted		Refs.
				Inherent	System-dependent/Both	
CH1	Limited battery	Underwater Data Acquisition Layer (Layer 1)	Reliability (Availability)	Credibility, Accuracy	Recoverability	2,3,5,11,13,14
CH2	Physical vulnerability		Reliability (Availability)	Credibility, Consistency	Recoverability	3,4,5,7,8,11,14
CH3	Lack of device output format standards		Compatibility (Interoperability)	Credibility	Compliance, Portability	3,5,7,14,15
CH4	Unreliable UAC links	Network Communication Layer (Layer 2)	Reliability (Fault Tolerance)	Credibility, Completeness	Recoverability	2,4,5,7,9,10,11,13,14
CH5	Missing raw data		Explainability	Credibility, Completeness	Understandability	13,14
CH6	Environmental impact of UAC		Performance efficiency (resource utilization)	Credibility	N/A	1,5,14
CH7	Low communication bandwidth and high latency of UAC and OTA links		Performance efficiency (capacity)	Credibility, Currentness, Completeness	N/A	6,13,14,16
CH8	Security vulnerability of UAC links		Security	Credibility	Availability, Confidentiality	3,6,11,12,14,19
CH9	Power-hungry data transmission over wireless communication channels		Energy Efficiency	Credibility	Recoverability	3,10,14
CH10	Complex data usage		Usability (Appropriateness recognizability)	N/A	Understandability	13,14,15
CH11	Lack of automatic QC procedures		Explainability	All	All	13,14,15,17
CH12	Heterogeneous data sources		Compatibility (Interoperability)		Compliance, Portability	13,15,18
CH13	Filter sensitive data (Business and Defence critical information)	Data Management Layer (Layer 3)	Security	N/A	Availability, Confidentiality	13,15
CH14	Lack of marketplace for data sharing and selling		Usability (accessibility - of data)	N/A	Availability, Confidentiality	13,14,15
CH15	Access control for data sharing		Security	N/A	Availability, Confidentiality	13,15